

Milestone: M2.3: Delivery of a Hackathon engaging three or more nominated ELIXIR Communities

Lead Participant: UOCHB

Author: John Hancock (SI), Karel Berka (CZ), Radka Svobodova (CZ),
Federica Quaglia (IT)

Due: 31 July 2025 (M18)

Date Of Completion: 19/06/2025

Means of Verification

[Hackathon meeting notes available](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

M2.3 Workshop and Hackathon organizers: John Hancock, Karel Berka, Radka Svobodova, Federica Quaglia

Workshop participants (including WP2 and WP3 members as well)

ELIXIR Communities representatives: Anastasis Oulas, George Gavriilidis, Gábor Erdős, Solenne Correard, Veit Schwammle, Lola Sanchez

Next action steps

Organizing M2.5 Delivery of a Hackathon engaging additional Communities for outreach

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